

The Influence Financial Literacy, Self-Discipline, and Financial Management on Consumer Behavior of Accounting Students in Triatma Mulya University Campus Environment

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ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
19 May 2026

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ABSTRACT

Consumptive behavior is an individual's tendency to purchase goods or services excessively without considering priority needs. In college students, this behavior often arises due to a lack of ability to manage finances, low financial literacy, and weak self-control. This study aims to analyze the influence of financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management on the consumptive behavior of accounting students on the Triatma Mulya University campus. This study uses a quantitative approach. The population in this study were 154 accounting students at Triatma Mulya University. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with a sample size of 106 respondents. The data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that financial literacy does not affect student consumptive behavior, while self-discipline and financial management have a negative effect on student consumptive behavior.

KEYWORDS: Financial Literacy, Self-Discipline, Financial Management, Consumer Behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

The campus environment is one factor that can influence consumer behavior. Consumer behavior is a common phenomenon among college students. Students often allocate their finances to purchase goods or services driven more by desire than need. This habit not only poses the risk of difficulty managing monthly, daily, or even weekly finances, but also a tendency to go into debt. It can also impact students' academic and psychological well-being. According to Lisdiana & Setiyono (2022), student consumer behavior is the tendency to purchase goods to meet lifestyle and social trends, rather than basic needs.

Yakoboski *et al.* (2022) reported that low financial literacy among young people in various countries is a factor driving excessive consumer behavior. In Indonesia, the Otoritas Jasa Keuangan on the 2022, that the national financial literacy rate had only reached 49.68%. This figure indicates that the public, including students, still has a low level of understanding of financial management. This situation is increasingly relevant to the reality of Triatma Mulya University Jembrana students living in the digital era, with easy access to e-commerce services, digital wallets, and various other consumer facilities. This can lead to consumer behavior among students, prioritizing what they want over what they need. Furthermore, many students are easily

influenced by unique items they see on social media, leading to a desire to purchase them.

Many important factors are believed to influence student consumer behavior, such as a lack of financial literacy, a lack of self-discipline to resist the temptation of unnecessary items, and a lack of proper financial management, which would require students to maintain personal bookkeeping detailing their income and expenses. Accounting students at Triatma Mulya University were chosen because they are in a unique situation for research: they learn financial theory in class but live in a digital era that encourages excessive consumption. Although theoretically, they should have good financial literacy, in reality, knowledge alone is not enough. According to previous research conducted by Putra & Sinarwati (2023), there is often a "gap" between theoretical understanding and actual behavior. These factors, such as the temptation of online shopping, the influence of social media, and peer pressure, can overwhelm financial knowledge. Therefore, this study aims to determine how accounting students in Jembrana, who learn theory in class but live in a digital world that encourages shopping, are able to manage their finances well and avoid consumptive behavior.

Financial literacy is a person's ability to understand and manage their money well, not only knowing how to use money, but also being able to plan, distinguish between

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needs and wants, save, and make the right decisions to maintain financial health. Pane & Payong (2024) state that financial literacy is a person's ability to understand basic concepts in financial management, such as budgeting, saving, investing, and using credit. According to Sihaloho & Hwihanus (2024), financial literacy is the ability to provide knowledge and skills to overcome financial problems. This awareness has a long-term impact on maintaining a normal, stable, safe, peaceful, and prosperous financial situation. Financial literacy provides an understanding of how to manage money wisely so that students are able to distinguish between needs and wants.

Self-discipline helps control impulsive shopping urges. Self-discipline is a person's ability to control themselves, regulate their actions, thoughts, and habits to remain consistent in achieving their goals, despite temptations, and to resist momentary desires and remain focused on what is more important. Self-discipline is included in the soft skills category, namely character traits that describe the qualities of a person's personality and behavior (personal attributes/behavioral traits). In general, self-discipline is about a person's ability to manage desires and impulses that arise, so that they remain focused on doing what they know is more important to do in order to achieve a goal (goals/purpose) (Schrader & Tangney, 2024).

Financial management is the process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling financial resources within an individual, organization, or company to achieve predetermined goals. Financial management aims to ensure that available funds are used effectively, efficiently, and sustainably. According to Sofiyana & Aryanto (2025), financial management is an individual's ability to manage their finances effectively, influenced by financial literacy, attitudes toward finance, and self-control. Good financial management, for example by preparing a budget and recording expenses, can maintain students' financial stability.

Self-discipline and financial management are two distinct concepts, though they often seem intertwined. Self-discipline is a person's psychological ability to control desires and resist temptation. It's like a "brake" that makes us think twice before buying something unnecessary. For example, when a disciplined student sees a big discount, he or she will be able to say to themselves, "Wait a minute, this isn't an urgent need." Meanwhile, financial management is the practical actions and technical skills involved in managing money. It's like a financial "map and travel log" that includes creating a budget, recording expenses, setting aside savings, and evaluating financial conditions. For example, a student who is good at financial management will create a shopping list and record every income and expense. Therefore, financial management is a crucial factor in fostering healthy and sustainable economic behavior among students and the general public.

Theoretically, this research is based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), which states that individual behavior is influenced by intentions, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived self-control. Financial literacy is one form of perceived self-control. Financial literacy can shape a rational attitude in using money, self-discipline is closely related to behavioral control, financial management is one form of perceived self-control. Self-discipline is one form of attitude. Self-discipline is a person's ability to control oneself in thinking, behaving, and acting to remain consistent with established values, goals, and rules despite temptations, emotional impulses, or momentary desires. Self-discipline is an important key to controlling consumptive behavior. The higher a person's self-discipline, the lower their tendency to be consumptive. Conversely, low self-discipline makes a person easily tempted by momentary desires, promotions, and social pressure, so that consumptive behavior increases. Financial management is a concrete manifestation of the application of this control. If someone has good financial management, it will reduce consumptive behavior. Therefore, this theory supports the relationship between financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management on students' consumer behavior.

Several studies have shown that Dinanti & Nesneri (2024) found that lifestyle and e-money use significantly contribute positively to consumer behavior among Generation Z in Pekanbaru City. Conversely, research conducted by Putra & Sinarwati (2023) showed that financial literacy and self-control play a negative and significant role in reducing consumer behavior. The findings indicate that financial literacy and self-control can reduce consumer behavior, while lifestyle and technology, such as e-money, increase spending. The importance of financial education and self-control strategies is emphasized to encourage healthier financial behavior among Generation Z. This strengthens the hypothesis that these three variables can also influence student consumer behavior.

Previous research largely supports this view. Dachlan *et al.* (2026) found that good financial management reduces excessive consumption among college students. Ulayya & Mujasih (2020), demonstrated that self-discipline plays a crucial role in curbing consumer behavior, while Lusardi & Mitchell (2023), emphasized the importance of financial literacy in making wise financial decisions. These findings demonstrate the positive influence of financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management on consumer behavior.

However, there are also studies with differing results. Wulandari *et al.* (2025) stated that financial literacy does not significantly influence consumer behavior because lifestyle and social environment factors are more dominant. Wulandari *et al.* (2025), also stated that financial discipline does not moderate the relationship between financial literacy, financial behavior, and financial attitudes on consumer behavior. These differing results indicate a gap in research to

clarify the relationship between variables in the context of college students.

In this study, consumer behavior is positioned as the dependent variable because it is the most visible end result of the interaction of various internal factors. Logically, it follows a causal sequence: first, a person has knowledge (financial literacy), then the ability to control themselves (self-discipline), then practical skills in managing money (financial management), and finally, all of these factors are manifested in the form of daily consumer behavior. This is also in line with previous research conducted by Kurnia & Hakim (2022), which positioned consumer behavior as the dependent variable to examine the influence of various causal factors. Consumer behavior was chosen as the dependent variable because it aligns with the research objective of determining how to reduce excessive consumption among college students. If financial management were used as the dependent variable, this research would change to "what influences students' financial management skills" instead of "what influences students' consumer behavior." Putra & Sinarwati (2023) study uses a similar approach, positioning consumer behavior as the outcome to be explained because its impact is directly felt on students' financial well-being.

This study aims to analyze the influence of financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management on the consumer behavior of accounting students on the Triatma Mulya University campus. This research was conducted due to the discrepancies in previous research findings and the limited research in the Jembrana area. Furthermore, this research is expected to serve as an evaluation tool to improve student financial education, enabling them to manage their finances wisely and reduce consumer behavior.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

A. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Icek Ajzen (1991), explains that individual behavior is influenced by intentions, which are formed by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Ajzen (2002) states that intentions are a direct factor that predicts a person's actual behavior. In addition, Conner & Armitage (1998) explain that TPB can be used to understand various human behaviors, including consumer behavior and financial management. This theory is used because it is able to explain the factors that influence student consumer behavior, both in terms of knowledge, self-control, and financial management. In this study, financial literacy shapes attitudes towards consumer behavior, self-discipline reflects behavioral control, and financial management helps individuals control spending, thereby influencing students' intentions to reduce consumer behavior.

B. Financial Literacy on Students Consumer Behavior

Financial literacy is a person's knowledge and understanding of financial concepts and risks, as well as the skills to use that knowledge to make effective decisions. Students with good financial literacy will be better able to understand the long-term consequences of unnecessary spending. This is in line with the Theory of Planned Behavior, which states that a person's attitude toward a behavior is shaped by their belief in the consequences of that behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Belief in the negative impacts of excessive consumption, understood through financial literacy, will shape a negative attitude toward consumptive behavior, thereby reducing the intention to behave in a consumptive manner. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Putra & Sinarwati (2023), Dinanti & Nesneri (2024), Rahmatia et al. (2025), which proved that financial literacy has a significant negative influence on student consumptive behavior, that the higher the financial literacy, the lower the tendency for consumptive behavior. Based on this, the following hypothesis can be formulated.

H1: Financial literacy has a negative effect on students consumer behavior.

C. Self-Discipline on Student Consumer Behavior

Self-discipline is an individual's ability to regulate and control behavior, thoughts, and emotions in the face of temptation and impulsiveness to achieve long-term goals. In a financial context, self-discipline enables students to stick to a budget and refrain from impulsive purchases. This concept is supported by the Theory of Planned Behavior through the dimension of perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). High self-discipline will increase students' perceived behavioral control over their financial management, thereby reducing the intention to make unnecessary and consumptive purchases. The results of this study align with previous research conducted by Putra & Sinarwati (2023), Kurnia & Hakim (2022), Wardoyo & Mahyuzar (2024), Wati et al. (2024), which showed that self-control has a significant negative effect on consumptive behavior. Based on this, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2: Self-discipline has a negative effect on consumer behavior in students.

D. Financial Management on Student Consumer Behavior

Financial management is the process of planning, budgeting, controlling, monitoring, and saving an individual's funds. Students who practice good financial management will have a higher awareness of their financial condition. This correlates with the Theory of Planned Behavior through the dimension of perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). Systematic financial management practices will increase

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students' perceptions of control over their finances, limit unplanned spending, and ultimately reduce their intention to engage in consumptive behavior. The results of this study align with previous research conducted by oleh Putra & Sinarwati (2023), Dachlan et al. (2026), Rozaini & Sitohang (2020), which showed that financial management has a significant negative effect on student consumptive behavior. Based on this, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H3: Financial management has a negative effect on student consumer behavior.

E. Research Model

This study explains the relationship between the independent variables, namely financial literacy (X1), self-discipline (X2), and financial management (X3) on the dependent variable, namely student consumer behavior (Y). This study examines the relationship or influence of the independent variables, namely financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management on student consumer behavior. The research model is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Research Model

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted at Triatma Mulya University. This research was conducted at Triatma Mulya University because it suited the research object and facilitated the researcher in obtaining relevant data to support the research process. The population in this study was all 154 accounting students at Triatma Mulya University. The sampling method used was purposive sampling, with a total of 106 observations. This study used a questionnaire for data collection with a four-point Likert scale and distributed via Google Form. The data analysis technique used was multiple linear regression analysis. This study used consumptive behavior as the dependent variable. The independent variables were financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management.

. The indicators and question items for each variable are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Research Instruments

Variables	Indicator
Consumer Behavior (Y) Siregar <i>et al.</i> (2023)	(1) impulsive buying, (2) desire to buy because of trends, (3) influenced by promotions, and (4) not considering needs
Financial Literacy (X1) Lusardi & Mitchell (2023) & OJK (2024)	(1) basic financial knowledge (savings, interest, inflation), (2) ability to manage personal finances, (3) understanding of financial products (banks, e-wallets, investments), and (4) awareness of risks and future financial planning.
Self-discipline (X2) Tangney <i>et al.</i> (2004)	(1) impulse control, (2) consistency in plans, (3) financial responsibility, and (4) control of unplanned purchases.
Financial Management (X3) Ananda & Rahmi (2023)	Financial management includes: (1) financial planning (budgeting), (2) expenditure control, (3) savings and investment, and (4) routine financial evaluation and recording.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results

A. Descriptive Statistical Test

Table 2. Results of Descriptive Statistical Test

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
X1	106	10,00	20,00	17,3585	2,54180
X2	106	10,00	20,00	15,1698	2,12232
X3	106	5,00	20,00	16,7642	3,03488
Y	106	5,00	20,00	9,0755	3,51784

Source: Processed data (2026)

Descriptive statistics show that the financial literacy variable has an average value of 17.3585 with an average score of 3.47 which is included in the "Strongly Agree" category, thus indicating that the respondents' level of financial literacy is classified as very good. The self-discipline variable has an average value of 15.1698 with an average score of 3.03 which is included in the "Agree" category, indicating that respondents have good self-discipline in controlling consumption behavior. Furthermore, the financial management variable has an average value of 16.7642 with an average score of 3.35 which is included in the "Agree" category, thus indicating

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that respondents have good financial management skills. Meanwhile, the consumptive behavior variable has an average value of 9.0755 with an average score of 1.82 which is included in the "Disagree" category, indicating that the level of respondents' consumptive behavior is classified as low.

B. Research Instrument Testing

Validity Test

Table 3. Results of Validity Test

Variables	Instrum ent Code	Pearson Correlation Value	Explanation
Financial Literacy (X1)	X1.1	0,934	Valid
	X1.2	0,897	Valid
	X1.3	0,908	Valid
	X1.4	0,902	Valid
	X1.5	0,808	Valid
Self- Discipline (X2)	X2.1	0,898	Valid
	X2.2	0,902	Valid
	X2.3	0,899	Valid
	X2.4	0,901	Valid
	X2.5	0,871	Valid
Financial Manageme nt (X3)	X3.1	0,919	Valid
	X3.2	0,927	Valid
	X3.3	0,891	Valid
	X3.4	0,891	Valid
	X3.5	0,921	Valid
Consumer Behavior (Y)	Y.1	0,942	Valid
	Y.2	0,941	Valid
	Y.3	0,931	Valid
	Y.4	0,922	Valid
	Y.5	0,899	Valid

Source: Processed data (2026)

The results of the validity test for each statement item contained in the questionnaire have Pearson correlation calculation results greater than 0.3 so that the statement items in this study can be declared valid.

Reliability Test

Table 4. Results of Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Explanation
Financial Literacy (X1)	0,931	Reliable
Self-Discipline (X2)	0,936	Reliable
Financial Management (X3)	0,948	Reliable
Consumer Behavior (Y)	0,957	Reliable

Source: Processed data (2026)

All research instruments were declared reliable because each statement item from the variables of financial

literacy, self-discipline, financial management and consumer behavior had a reliability coefficient greater than 0.7.

C. Classical Assumption Test

Hypothesis testing was conducted using multiple linear regression analysis, which had previously been validated based on classical assumptions. The results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed a significance value of 0,200, indicating a normal data distribution. The results of the multicollinearity test showed a tolerance value greater than 0.10 and a variance inflation factor less than 10, indicating the absence of multicollinearity. This regression model also showed no signs of heteroscedasticity.

D. Hypothesis Test (t-test)

Table 5. Results of the t-test

Variable.	Coef.	t-Statistic.	Sig.	Prediction
X1	-0,205	-1,253	0,213	H1
X2	-0,230	-1,418	0,016	H2(-)
X3	-0,123	-0,887	0,038	H3(-)
Constant	18,195	6,008	0,001	
Adjusted R-Square	0,260			
Probability (F-statistic)	3,249		0,002	
N	106			

** Sig. on level 0,05 (p<0,05)

Source: Processed data (2026)

The model fit test yielded an adjusted R-squared value of 0.260, indicating that the variables of financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management only explain 26% of consumer behavior. The remaining 74% is attributed to other variables outside the scope of this research model. The F value is 3.249 with a significance level of 0.002 < 0.05. This indicates that financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management simultaneously influence consumer behavior.

The financial literacy test showed a significance value of 0.213, indicating that the results did not support H1. The self-discipline test showed a significance value of 0.016, thus supporting H2. Meanwhile, the financial management test showed a significance value of 0.038, thus supporting H3.

Discussions

A. The Influence of Financial Literacy on Students Consumer Behavior

The first hypothesis states that financial literacy negatively influences consumer behavior. The financial literacy variable has a regression coefficient of -0.205 and a significance value of 0.213, which is greater than 0.05. The

results show that financial literacy does not influence the consumer behavior of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University, thus rejecting H1. This means that financial literacy does not influence student consumer behavior.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), financial literacy is related to attitude toward behavior, namely how an individual's understanding and knowledge influence financial decision-making (Ajzen, 1991). Theoretically, the higher a person's level of financial literacy, the better their ability to manage and use finances rationally, thereby reducing consumptive behavior. However, the results of this study indicate that financial literacy does not influence student consumptive behavior. Students who have a good understanding of finance are not necessarily able to apply it in their daily lives (Aini & Rahayuningsih, 2024). Students still tend to make purchases based on emotional factors, social influences, social media trends, and lifestyles that develop in their social circles. Furthermore, students often prioritize wants over needs even though they understand the concept of financial management (Akbar et al. 2023). This condition indicates that financial knowledge is not strong enough to suppress student consumptive behavior (Wati et al. 2024). High or low financial literacy does not determine the level of student consumptive behavior.

The results of this study align with those of Akbar et al. (2023), Wulandari et al. (2025), Kurnia & Hakim (2022), Aini & Rahayuningsih (2024), Rahmayani et al. (2025), Utomo et al. (2024), Gari & Prima (2026) and Wati et al. (2024), which show that financial literacy has no effect on consumer behavior. However, these results are inconsistent with those of Putra & Sinarwati (2023), Dinanti & Nesneri (2024), Rahmatia et al. (2025), which show that financial literacy negatively impacts consumer behavior.

B. The Influence of Self-Discipline on Student Consumer Behavior

The second hypothesis states that self-discipline negatively influences consumer behavior. The self-discipline variable has a regression coefficient of -0.230, and a significance value of 0.016, which is less than 0.05. The results of the study indicate that self-discipline negatively influences consumer behavior of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University, thus H2 is accepted. These results indicate that better self-discipline will reduce student consumer behavior.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), self-discipline is related to perceived behavioral control, namely an individual's ability to control behavior and make informed decisions (Ajzen, 1991). The higher an individual's self-control, the greater their ability to avoid consumptive behavior and use money more wisely (Wati et al. 2024). Students with good self-discipline are able to resist the urge to buy goods impulsively, are not easily

influenced by promotions or social environments, and prioritize needs over wants (Wardoyo & Mahyuzar, 2024). This condition encourages students to be more careful in spending and more rational in making purchasing decisions (Kurnia & Hakim, 2022). Students with high self-discipline are better able to control consumptive behavior because they have good control over their financial behavior.

The results of this study align with those of Kurnia & Hakim (2022), Wardoyo & Mahyuzar (2024), Wati et al. (2024), Putra & Sinarwati (2023), which stated that self-discipline negatively influences consumer behavior. However, these results disagree with those of Novianti & Suwaidi (2024), Salsabilla & Wicaksono (2025), Gari & Prima (2026), which stated that self-discipline has no effect on consumer behavior.

C. The Influence of Financial Management on Student Consumer Behavior

The third hypothesis states that financial management negatively influences consumer behavior. The financial management variable has a regression coefficient of -0.123 and a significance value of 0.038, which is less than 0.05. The results indicate that financial management negatively influences consumer behavior of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University, thus H3 is accepted. These results indicate that better financial management will reduce student consumer behavior.

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), financial management is related to perceived behavioral control, namely the individual's actual actions in managing and using finances in a planned manner (Ajzen, 1991). The better an individual's ability to manage finances, the greater their ability to control spending and avoid consumptive behavior (Rozaini & Sitohang, 2020). Students who have good financial management tend to be able to create budgets, manage income and expenses, set aside money for savings, and determine needs priorities more wisely (Putra & Sinarwati, 2023). This condition helps students be more rational in making purchases, thereby reducing the tendency to overspend (Dachlan et al. 2026). Students who have good financial management will be better able to suppress consumptive behavior because they have more focused financial planning and control.

The results of this study align with those of Putra & Sinarwati (2023), Dachlan et al. (2026), Rozaini & Sitohang (2020), which stated that financial management negatively impacts consumer behavior. However, these results differ from those of Akbar et al. (2023), which stated that financial management has no effect on consumer behavior.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to analyze the factors influencing the consumer behavior of accounting students at Triatma Mulya University by examining the influence of financial literacy,

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self-discipline, and financial management on their consumer behavior. The study sample consisted of 106 accounting students who met the research criteria: active students in the accounting study program, having taken the Introduction to Accounting course, and being at least in their third semester. Based on the analysis and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Financial literacy has no effect on consumer behavior. This means that high or low financial literacy is not a determining factor in students' consumer behavior.
2. Self-discipline has a negative effect on consumer behavior. This means that the higher the self-discipline, the lower the student's consumer behavior.
3. Financial management has a negative effect on consumer behavior. This means that the better the financial management, the lower the student's consumer behavior.

LIMITATION

This study's limitations are that it only involved accounting students at Triatma Mulya University as respondents, so the results cannot be widely generalized. Furthermore, the Adjusted R Square value of 0.260 indicates that only 26% of consumer behavior can be explained by financial literacy, self-discipline, and financial management, while the remaining 74% is influenced by factors outside the research model.

SUGGESTION

Further research can expand the scope of the study by involving respondents from various universities or different study programs and adding other independent variables such as lifestyle, peer influence, social media, and social environmental factors that can influence student consumer behavior.

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